

Studies on the Reaction of Oxomolybdenum(v) Ion using 2-(2'-Quinoly)benzimidazole as a Potential Ligand

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The role of oxomolybdenum species with d^1 -configuration in the environment of biologically active organic compounds having $-N=C-C=N-$ donor sites has been established through our previous communications¹. Immense biological activities of benzimidazole derivatives together with their similarities with the compounds like 2,2'-bipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline and 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzothiazole, provoked us to study the behaviour of MoO^{3+} , where molybdenum is in quinquevalent state with the compound 2-(2'-quinoly)benzimidazole (Quinbmz) under the influence of diverse anionic medium like Cl^- and Br^- . Present communication deals with the synthesis and characterisation of some Mo^V compounds using 2-(2'-quinoly)benzimidazole as metal binding substance.

Results and Discussion

The basicity of 2-(2'-quinoly)benzimidazole is such that the interaction of the species $MoOX_3^-$ in $> 9 N$ HX acidity always results the formation of the solid salts $QuinbmzH_2[MoOX_3]$. The strong binding property of the ligand has been established through the study of the dehydrohalogenation reaction of such salts carried out with solvents like acetonitrile and absolute ethanol,

This reaction leads to the synthesis of the nonelectrolytic compounds $[MoOX_3.Quinbmz]$. It has been observed that this compounds obtained with absolute ethanol and acetonitrile are of same composition but different in colours. This may be due to the fact that they are colour isomers with respect to each other. As the compounds are insoluble in nonpolar solvents, their dipole moment measurements were not possible. The molar conductivities of all the complexes were measured in acetonitrile medium using 'Dip type' cell. The molar conductance values 111.00 and 115.62 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2$ for the chloro and bromo salts respectively, are incompatible with 1 : 1 electrolytes and for the nonelectrolytes the values ranging between 11.21 and 12.47 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2$ (Table 1) are much less than the binary electrolytes². The room temperature magnetic susceptibilities of the salts and their nonelectrolytic derivatives are found in the range 1.68–1.79 B.M., which confirm the presence of MoO^{3+} (Table 1) unit in these compounds with d^1 -configuration of molybdenum. From epr spectra the average $\langle g \rangle$ values were calculated and these values also support d^1 -configuration of the oxometal ion³.

Ir spectra of the complexes display a very strong absorption at 950–980 cm^{-1} , assigned to the symmetric stretching mode of the terminal $Mo=O$ band⁴. Electronic

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA FOR THE COMPLEXES

Sl no.	Compd.	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)				Oxidation state of Mo	$\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$	μ_{eff}^* B.M.	$\langle g \rangle$	$\nu_{Mo=O}$ cm^{-1}
		Mo	N	Cl	Br					
1.	QuinbmzH ₂ [MoOCl ₅]	17.43 (17.86)	7.78 7.82	32.77 33.08	–	4.93	111.00	1.79 (299)	1.82	950
2.	(a) [MoOCl ₃ .Quinbmz] Bright red, obtained from ethanol	20.54 (20.70)	8.78 9.06	22.30 22.98	–	4.85	12.47	1.77 (298)	1.90	950
	(b) [MoOCl ₃ .Quinbmz] Chocolate, obtained from acetonitrile	20.49 (20.70)	8.82 9.06	22.92 22.98	–	5.01	12.06	1.76 (298)	1.89	950
3.	QuinbmzH ₂ [MoOCl ₅]	12.69 (12.64)	5.58 5.53	– –	52.76 52.70	4.87	115.62	1.68 (300)	1.93	980
4.	(a) [MoOBr ₃ .Quinbmz] Light yellow, obtained from ethanol	15.90 (16.08)	7.46 7.03	– –	40.32 40.20	4.96	11.21	1.71 (299)	1.90	965
	(b) [MoOBr ₃ .Quinbmz] Light orange, obtained from acetonitrile	15.95 (16.08)	7.30 7.03	– –	40.42 40.20	4.93	11.44	1.73 (299)	1.89	970

*Value in parentheses indicates the temperature (K) at which magnetic susceptibility was measured.

spectra of the complexes were recorded in acetonitrile (A.R.). $\text{QuinbmzH}_2[\text{MoOX}_5]$ ($X = \text{Cl}$ and Br) revealed bands at 690–696 and 463 which may be assigned to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (I) and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ transitions respectively. The bands around 356–370, 294–322, 262–284 and 236–248 may be assigned to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (II), ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ (I), ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ (II) and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (III) respectively. The bands of the nonelectrolytes $[\text{MoOX}_3.\text{Quinbmz}]$ at 710–720, 442–452, 330–354, 290–314, 250–290 and 222–250 may be assigned to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (I), ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$, $L \rightarrow \text{Mo}$ (charge transfer), ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ (I), ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ (II) and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (III) respectively. These assignments are fairly in good agreement with those of the similar compounds having octahedral geometry⁵.

Experimental

2-(2'-Quinoly)benzimidazoliumoxopentachloromolybdate(v), QuinbmzH₂[MoOCl₅]: To the bright green solution containing $[\text{MoOCl}_5]^{2-}$ ion (obtained from 1 g of MoO_3), a solution of 2-(2'-quinoly)benzimidazole ($\text{MoO}_3 : \text{Quinbmz} = 1 : 1$; 1.8 g) in 12 M HCl was added with stirring in ice-cold condition. The resulting greenish yellow solid was washed with 12 M HCl and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, yield ~ 1.72 g.

Oxotrichloro-2-(2'-quinoly)benzimidazole molybdenum(v), [MoOCl₃.Quinbmz]. *Method A*: The parent salt $\text{QuinbmzH}_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (1 g) was refluxed with absolute ethanol (20 ml) for 1 h under positive pressure of the solvent. The resulting bright red solid was washed with ethanol (5 ml) and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, yield ~0.65 g.

Method B: The parent salt $\text{QuinbmzH}_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (1 g) was refluxed with acetonitrile (25 ml) in identical manner as above and a chocolate coloured solid of identical composition was obtained. It was washed with acetonitrile (5

ml) and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, yield ~0.70 g.

2-(2'-Quinoly)benzimidazolium oxopentabromomolybdate(v), QuinbmzH₂[MoOBr₅]: To the brown solution containing $[\text{MoOBr}_5]^{2-}$ ion (obtained from 1 g of MoO_3), a solution of 2-(2'-quinoly)benzimidazole (1.8 g) in 9 M HBr was added in portions with constant stirring in ice-cold condition. The resulting shining brown crystals were crystallised from HBr, washed with HBr (2 ml) and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, yield ~1.8 g.

Oxotribromo-2-(2'-quinoly)benzimidazole molybdenum(v), [MoOBr₃.Quinbmz]. *Method A*: The parent salt $\text{QuinbmzH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ (1 g) was refluxed with absolute ethanol (20 ml) under the positive pressure of the solvent for 1 h. The light yellow solid obtained on cooling it to room temperature, was washed with ethanol (5 ml) and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, yield ~0.52 g.

Method B: The salt $\text{QuinbmzH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ (1 g) was refluxed with acetonitrile (25 ml) in identical manner as described above for 2 h and then cooled. The resulting light orange solid was washed with acetonitrile (5 ml) and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, yield ~ 0.65 g.

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